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PERFORM ADDITION AND MULTIPLICATION OPERATIONS IN EXCEL

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ANNOTATION

This article analyzes the possibilities of mathematical functions of the Excel table editor. Among the mathematical functions, multiplication and addition were used and the result was obtained using this operation. Information is provided on the use of multiplication and addition operations.

Keywords. *Excel program, table editor, toolbar, function, division, multiplication.*

Microsoft Excel (sometimes called Microsoft Office Excel) is a program for working with spreadsheets created by Microsoft Corporation for Microsoft Windows, Windows NT and Mac OS, as well as Android, iOS, Windows Phone. It offers economic-statistical calculations, graphic tools. The programming language of Excel 2008 on the Mac OS X platform is VBA (Visual Basic for Applications). Microsoft Excel is a component of Microsoft Office, and today Excel is among the most popular applications in the world [1].

A computer has several application software. Among them, the Excel program is called a table editor. Because Excel mainly works with tables. In addition, it has the

ability to perform calculations. An Excel spreadsheet has several functions. They can be used in various fields. For example, when performing accounting operations, outputting times, outputting some values, etc.

Before starting work, we will enter MS Excel. Then we go to the “Formula” section from the equipment panel. There are various functions there. For example, the functions “Mathematicheskije”, “Poslednie”, “Data i vremya”, “Logicheskie” and so on. We will consider the implementation of some of them.

Picture 1. MS Excel table editor interface.

Let’s try using some of the commands in the “Mathematics” section. First of all, we need to write down the list. We enter the “Mathematicheskije” section. Then we select the “MUMNOJ” command from among the commands.

	A	B	C	D	E	F
1						
2		№	Mahsulotlar	Narxi	Og'irligi	Umumiy summa
3		1	Olma	3000	5	
4		2	Anor	5000	4	
5		3	Apelsin	4500	4	
6		4	Nok	3500	7	
7		5	Mandarin	6000	2	
8		6	Banan	5500	3	
9						
10		Jami				
11						

Picture 2. List

Then we determine the place of the numbers being multiplied. The location should be set to Massiv 1 and Massiv 2.

Picture 4. The process of performing multiplication

Picture 5. Determining the location of the action.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G
1							
2		№	Mahsulotlar	Narxi	Og'irligi	Umumiy summa	
3		1	Olma	3000	5	15000	
4		2	Anor	5000	4		
5		3	Apelsin	4500	4		
6		4	Nok	3500	7		
7		5	Mandarin	6000	2		
8		6	Banan	5500	3		
9							
10		Jami					
11							

Picture 6. Result.

“Ok” button is clicked. The result will be as shown in Figure 6. If you drag down the corner, Excel will multiply everything. Same as in Picture 7.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G
1							
2		№	Mahsulotlar	Narxi	Og'irligi	Umumiy summa	
3		1	Olma	3000	5	15000	
4		2	Anor	5000	4	20000	
5		3	Apelsin	4500	4	18000	
6		4	Nok	3500	7	24500	
7		5	Mandarin	6000	2	12000	
8		6	Banan	5500	3	16500	
9							
10		Jami					
11							

Picture 7. Total all results.

In conclusion, it can be said that the Excel table editor is one of the most used and very useful applications for users. It is very convenient to work with tables. In addition, Excel has the ability to work with various functions.

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